

Social origin and social context inequalities in post-16 educational pathways

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Abstract

At age 16, young people in England make important decisions about their educational pathways. The ‘academic pathway’ is the result of enrolling in A level qualifications, which are typically necessary for admission to undergraduate education. Within the academic pathway, evidence suggests that a young persons’ A level subject choices additionally shape their access to the selective universities. To date, there is little evidence on trends in the participation of young people from disadvantaged backgrounds in these ‘academic tracks’ in the English education system. In this paper, we provide new evidence using data from three cohorts across 15 years: the Next Steps study, Millennium Cohort Study and COVID Social Mobility and Opportunities study. We focus on tracking levels of inequalities in whether to engage in academic pathways based on social origin (family background) and social context (social deprivation by geography). Results provide little evidence of change in the proportion of low socioeconomic status young people studying for A level qualifications, or in the reduction of inequalities in those studying for high return subjects. There is, however, consistent indication that social origin is more predictive of decisions made at age 16 than social context. Further research will engage with the historical contexts of these cohort studies (i.e., the raising of the participation age) to understand the impact of specific policies regarding socioeconomic inequalities in education pathways.

Introduction

To improve social mobility in England, more young people from low socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds need to achieve Level 3 (equivalent to end of secondary school) qualifications (Crawford et al., 2017), as achieving these qualifications has been repeatedly demonstrated to increase lifetime earning potential (Card, 1999; Crawford et al., 2016). Increased education levels are also associated with wider benefits for young people's health, wellbeing and criminality, among others (Davies et al., 2018; Farquharson et al., 2024). Yet persistent socioeconomic disparities remain (Anders, 2012a; Crawford, 2014). As in most countries, admissions to universities in England are dependent on succeeding in qualifications at the end of secondary education. Young people enrol in these qualifications at age 16, making this period a key education transition with significant consequences. Differences in the pathways taken at age 16 can, therefore, exacerbate existing social inequalities and, hence, they are vital to understand and address.

One pathway is enrolment in A level qualifications, which are specialised academic qualifications most commonly required for admission to university undergraduate programmes (Department for Education, 2024) and represent an 'academic pathway'. Despite efforts to diversify pathways to university education in recent years, it has continued to be very difficult to enrol in university without enrolling in A levels (Maris, 2025). Moreover, within the 'academic pathway', the subjects that a young person decides to study have also been linked to their likelihood of admission to the UK's most prestigious universities (Dilnot, 2016; Dilnot et al., 2023).

An alternative pathway is enrolment in vocational education, including technical qualifications, apprenticeships and in-work training, which often result in qualifications conducive to either subsequent further education in technical subjects or entering the workforce, and thus represents a 'technical / vocational pathway'. Until 2015, English young people also had the option of ceasing education entirely at age 16.

In this paper we focus specifically on changes over time in young people from different backgrounds taking these different routes. Given the labour market benefits that can accrue from a young person's pursuit of an 'academic' pathway at age 16, this provides an important perspective about how an important aspect of social mobility may be changing over time. To achieve this, we combine data from three cohort studies across nearly two decades representing 16-year-olds' routes through this key transition. By comparing inequalities in these cohorts, we provide new evidence on whether the chances of low SES (defined by social origin and social context) young people a) enrolling in academic qualifications and b) within academic qualifications, enrolling in more 'facilitating' subjects (Dilnot, 2018) than others has changed over 15 years between 2006 and 2021.

Institutional setting

In England, at age 16, there are multiple important decisions to be made regarding subsequent education and training. These decisions result in distinct pathways and are demonstrated in *Figure 1*. Although we use the term 'decisions', we note that it is important to recognise that for some young people these will be highly constrained depending upon factors including prior attainment and opportunities available within their local area. We stress that we are not seeking

to imply that they have full agency over these decisions, but alternative ways of describing them have proved cumbersome.

[Figure 1 here]

Decision 1: Should I remain in education/training?

From 1972 until 2015, 16-year-olds were faced with the decision of whether to continue their education or training. If they continued, they would study for further qualifications; if they did not continue, they would leave school with the lowest levels of qualifications (if any) and either enter the labour market for a ‘job without training’ or be not in education, employment or training (NEET). The group that did not remain in education or training were more likely to be low SES (Crawford et al., 2011), male, White and children of parents with low levels of qualifications themselves (Spielhofer et al., 2007). Although the raising of the participation age in 2015 from age 16 to age 18 officially removed the option to cease education or training at age 16, as there has been little to no enforcement of this policy (Dickson et al., 2025), this decision does effectively persist. The results of Decision 1 are an important means by which social inequalities persist in the education system and in the labour market.

Decision 2: Should I pursue academic or technical qualifications?

Assuming that they decide to remain in education or training, young people must then choose between pursuing ‘academic’ qualifications (i.e., A levels) or ‘technical/vocational’ qualifications (i.e., BTECs, NVQs, other qualifications). Enrolling exclusively for academic qualifications (at least three A levels) is an unofficial ‘academic track’ in the English system, as this is typically the minimum requirement for the majority of undergraduate admissions (Dilnot, 2018). Pursuing only academic qualifications is the pathway most associated with reaching the top earnings quartile group, while pursuing only technical qualifications is the pathway most associated with ending up in the bottom earnings quartile group (Social Mobility Commission, 2021). As noted above, this is not an entirely free decision, not least as enrolment is dependent on performance in GCSEs at age 16, which consist of eight to ten examinations across a wide range of subjects (including core requirements of English, maths and science).

Lower SES young people in England on average achieve lower GCSE grades (Farquharson et al., 2024) and are, therefore, less likely to be eligible to study A levels. Thus, Decision 2 both has substantial socioeconomic consequences and is shaped by socioeconomic inequalities. Unsurprisingly, there are SES differences in whether young people pursue the ‘academic’ track. Crawford et al. (2011) found that English 16-year-olds in the most deprived social contexts are 14 percentage points more likely to attend institutions focused on technical and vocational training than their more advantaged peers. Putting this into an international context, this is comparable to the vast SES differences between the chances that young people enrol in the more academic ‘gymnasium’ schools compared to schools oriented towards vocational careers in Germany (Entorf & Davoli, 2019).

Decision 3: Should I enrol in ‘facilitating’ academic subjects?

Young people who pursue an ‘academic pathway’ must also select the subjects they intend to study for their A level examinations. Unlike some European education systems that

separate subjects into defined ‘tracks’, some of which are known to be more prestigious than others (i.e., série S or the ‘science track’ for the French baccalauréat, Le Nevé, 2018), the English system does not feature defined combinations of subjects. Despite this, there are differences in the esteem that subjects hold for university admissions: Dilnot (2018) divides A level subjects into ‘facilitating’ (e.g., Biology, History, Mathematics), ‘useful’ (e.g., Economics, English literature, Music) and less suitable (e.g., Business, Law, Media Studies) categories. Non-advantageous combinations of A level subject choices limit young people’s competitiveness for admission to the highest-status UK universities (referred to as the Russell Group) and degree subjects.

For a period, this information was made visible through the Russell Group’s publication ‘Informed Choices’ (Russell Group, 2016) that listed these ‘facilitating’ subjects, but this was discontinued. Therefore, this Decision 3 once again constitutes a ‘hidden curriculum’ of which lower SES young people may be less aware. Among equally high-achieving young people, approximately three-fifths of higher SES young people select at least one ‘facilitating’ subject, compared to only one-third of lower SES young people (Sammons et al., 2015). This is particularly true for Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) subjects: echoing French findings that higher SES young people are more likely to pursue the ‘sciences’ pathway than their peers (République Française, 2021), higher SES young people are 50% more likely to enrol in STEM A level subjects than their lower SES peers (Sammons et al., 2015). Young people’s subject choices maintain socioeconomic divisions: STEM degrees have a comparatively greater earning potential (Belfield et al., 2018) and admissions to STEM undergraduate courses in the UK requires studying facilitating STEM A level subjects.

Summary

In England, age 16 represents an important point for division into education or training pathways, including potentially leaving them entirely, following an ‘academic’ pathway, and, within this, selection of ‘facilitating’ subjects. This study therefore seeks to provide a richer understanding of whether social inequalities in these decisions have changed over time and how SES (defined both as social origin and social context) interacts with these decisions.

Data

We seek to explore this issue and test our hypothesis using data from three existing longitudinal cohort studies of young people born between 1989 and 2005. These datasets provide a rich set of information on their backgrounds, including their social origin and social context. Furthermore, by linking each dataset to administrative data from the UK’s National Pupil Database, we are able to measure our outcome of qualifications pursued at 16-18 years old, as well as accounting for their prior educational attainment, which provides crucial context to understanding their decisions. To ease comparisons with other studies, and to reduce the risk of migration history affecting findings, the samples from all three cohort studies were limited to cohort members who were born in the UK. The three cohorts are as follows:

- 1) Next Steps (NS) includes a sample of children born between 1989 and 1990 and initially followed a sample of approximately 16,000 adolescents (University College London, UCL Institute of Education, et al., 2025b). This study first collected data when participants were approximately 14 years old and has followed them until the age of 32

years old (at time of writing). Data were collected every year between ages 14 and 19 and then approximately twice a decade since. This dataset is linked with education administrative data (University College London, UCL Institute of Education, et al., 2025a), including cohort members' GCSE and A level results. Cohort members are clustered in schools, schools in low socioeconomic status were purposely oversampled and minority ethnic students were oversampled within schools. Members of this cohort entered these pathways in 2006.

- 2) The Millennium Cohort Study (MCS) includes a sample of children born across the United Kingdom, although, in this study, to facilitate harmonised cross-cohort comparisons, we exclusively focus on its English sample, all of whom were born between September 2000 and September 2001 (University College London, UCL Institute of Education, Centre for Longitudinal Studies, et al., 2025; University of London & Centre for Longitudinal Studies, 2024, 2025). Approximately 18,000 families were recruited for this cohort study and data was collected from 9 months until age 23 with intervals of 2 to 6 years. Similar to Next Steps, it has substantial data linkages with education records. Unlike Next Steps, recruitment was not clustered by school. Instead 'electoral wards' across the UK were used for recruitment, with a purposeful oversampling of low socioeconomic status and ethnic children. Members of this cohort entered these pathways in 2017.
- 3) The COVID Social Mobility and Opportunities (COSMO) study includes a sample of children born between 2004 and 2005 (Anders, Calderwood, et al., 2024a, 2024b). It was started during the COVID-19 pandemic to understand better the unequal impacts of the global pandemic on the education and employment opportunities of English young people who were in Year 11 in the 2020-2021 academic year. To date, it has had two data collection waves when the participants were 16 to 17 years old and 17 to 18 years old. Like Next Steps, COSMO's design features stratified and clustered sampling, including deliberate over-sampling of some groups to improve power to consider differences between those groups. Participants were clustered and recruited from 500 schools, yielding an initial sample of 13,000 cohort members. Members of this cohort entered these pathways in 2021.

Members of all three cohorts were presented with the option of making *Decisions 2* and *3* when they reached age 16, which resulted in three academic pathways (see *Figure 1*). We distinguish these pathways for each cohort member using three binary variables:

Pathway 1: Among the population, what was the outcome of *Decision 2*, i.e., did cohort members pursue the 'academic track' of exclusively pursuing at least three A levels (1) or pursue any other activity (i.e., 'technical / vocational track' or ceasing education or training) (0)?

Pathway 2a: Among the population, what was the outcome of *Decision 3*, i.e., did cohort members pursue a 'facilitating' set of A levels (defined as enrolled in three A level subjects, at least two of which are listed as facilitating by Dilnot, 2018) (1) or any other activity (i.e., fewer than two facilitating subjects, fewer than three A level subjects, technical or vocational qualifications or ceasing education or training) (0)?

Pathway 2b: Among cohort members pursuing A levels, what was the outcome of *Decision 3*, i.e., did cohort members pursue a ‘facilitating’ set of A levels (same definition as for Pathway 2a) (1) or another combination of A levels (0)?

These variables are derived from versions of the cohort members’ examination enrolment records taken from the data linked from each cohort study with the National Pupil Database. It should be noted that cohort members could have partially participated in or ‘dropped out’ from a qualification, but this is not reliably recorded across datasets as we only observe their final qualification. It was also not possible to differentiate between English Literature (a facilitating subject) and English Language (a non-facilitating subject) in the COSMO dataset; thus, any reference to an English A level was considered facilitating in this dataset.

Regarding *Decision 2*, 37% of the Next Steps study, 44% of the Millennium Cohort Study and 56% of the COSMO study took three or more A levels, representing a substantial increase over the three cohorts. Given the findings of Doyle et al. (2023) and Prior and Leckie (2025), it should be noted that the particularly high figure for COSMO may reflect the aftermath of the use of teacher assessed grades for GCSEs in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic. This is because teacher assessed grades were more generous than external examinations, meaning that more pupils from all backgrounds were likely to have greater access to this pathway for this cohort. Regarding *Decision 3*, 19% of the Next Steps study, 22% of the Millennium Cohort Study and 29% of the COSMO study took three A levels, at least two of which were facilitating subjects. This apparent increase in the COSMO cohort appears to primarily reflect that larger movement into A levels in general as, among those who studied three or more A levels, 52% of the Next Steps study, 50% of the Millennium Cohort Study and 53% of the COSMO studied at least two facilitating subjects.

Our primary independent variables of interest are social origin and social context. SES in England can be difficult to operationalise, and studies of educational outcomes have varied in their focus on family income, parental education and area-based deprivation. Therefore, this study differentiates between social origin and social context as two theoretically related but distinct predictors.

Rather than focusing on a single factor, this study derived social origin in each dataset by extracting the principal factor (i.e., the one that explains the most variance with a single measure) from a factor analysis of 1) highest level of parental education (levels: none; secondary school; post-secondary qualification), 2) parental occupational status (levels: managerial; intermediate; manual or none), 3) parental home ownership (levels: yes; no). This composite was then standardised by dividing the sample into quintile groups (1 = highest SES; 5 = lowest SES) within each dataset for cross-cohort comparison. This follows the approach taken by Anders (2017).

In addition, as a proxy of the social disadvantage that each cohort member faces in their prospects, social context was derived from each child’s Income Deprivation Affecting Children Index (IDACI) scores. IDACI is constructed by measuring the proportion of children under 16 years old in a geographical area of approximately 1,500 people living in a household considered as income deprived. Again, the sample was divided into quintile groups (1 = least deprived; 5 = most deprived) using these scores.

We also control for a range of cohort member-level characteristics using the rich data available in the cohort studies. This is important both to allow us to focus on inequalities associated with SES net of other potential explanatory factors for entry to these pathways, and as it may help to deal with residual compositional differences between our cohort studies despite our attempts at harmonisation. Ethnicity was collected in each cohort study using the same categories as the most recent UK census prior to the measurement occasion. As these categories changed over time, for cross-cohort harmonisation, values were recoded into Asian, Black, Mixed, Other, and White. Due to comparatively low numbers, Mixed and Other were combined.

Gender identity was inconsistently measured between cohort studies. Sex at birth was recorded by all three studies but only COSMO consistently asked for self-defined gender identity. Gender identity was not asked in NS during the measurement occasions used in these analyses and not by MCS before age 16. Therefore, although the variable is referred to as ‘gender’, participants’ values for gender from the NS and MCS studies needed to be assumed to be equivalent to their sex at birth.

Academic attainment at age 16 is known to affect participation in further education and training. This is because admission to A level courses is partly determined by GCSE grades and because GCSE results provide young people with their clearest indicator of academic potential, which guides their decisions (Foskett et al., 2008). We use cohort members’ performance across their highest or ‘best 8’ GCSE scores, which acts as a summary of their education (see Anders et al., 2022; Anders, Green, et al., 2024 for examples of precedent). There are cross-cohort differences in the scales on which GCSEs were awarded due to a national change in GCSE grades over this period. For NS, grades were on a scale between A* (highest) and G (lowest); for MCS, grades were on the same scale as MCS, except for mathematics, English literature and English language, which were on a scale between 9 (highest) and 1 (lowest); for COSMO, all grades were on the 9–1 scale. To harmonise these values, letter grades were translated into numbers following the approximate conversion scale in Stopforth et al. (2025). This resulted in a potential score out of 72, albeit with a slightly lower maximum for NS and MCS of 67.

The curriculum studied by cohort members before making their decisions at age 16 could also matter, especially for entering an ‘academic pathway’. We proxied for this by deriving a binary variable (1 = Yes, 0 = No) indicating whether pupils studied towards GCSEs that together would qualify for the government’s English Baccalaureate (EBacc) measure (if achieved), which is considered a broad and relatively prestigious foundation for further academic study, including the ‘academic track’ (Long & Danechi, 2019; Moulton et al., 2018). To be considered to have achieved the EBacc pupils have to achieve a ‘good pass’ in: 1) mathematics, 2) English language or English literature, 3) an ancient or modern foreign language, 4) three sciences or Combined Science and 5) either geography or history — although, to reiterate, our measure focuses on whether they studied towards these, rather than achievement. The EBacc was introduced after the NS cohort but before the MCS and COSMO cohorts completed GCSEs; however, many in the NS cohort did study this combination of subjects (Anders et al., 2018).

[Tables 1 and 2 here]

Having defined these background characteristics, we break down the proportions of cohort members who take each pathway in *Tables 1* and *2*, which report the percentage of each cohort who pursue the ‘academic track’ pathway and studied at least two facilitating subjects, respectively, and present the proportions within each social origin, social context, ethnicity and gender identity group, along with average prior attainment and take up of EBacc. Patterns in these descriptive statistics suggest that being of a more advantaged social origin and social context were associated with a greater likelihood of being in the ‘academic track’ and studying two facilitating subjects. However, they also demonstrate a) inequalities associated with other characteristics including being non-White, female, having higher academic achievement and studying a facilitating curriculum at age 16, and b) residual compositional differences between the cohorts despite our harmonisation efforts. It is important that we seek to account for these differences when seeking to understand differences in socioeconomic inequalities between cohorts.

Methods

Regression modelling was used to understand the association between SES and entry to each of the pathways after accounting for characteristics noted in *Tables 1* and *2*. Specifically, we use binary choice generalised linear models with a probit link function of the form:

$$P(Y) = \alpha + \beta_1 SES_i + \beta'_2 IDACI_i + \mathbf{X}_i + \varepsilon_i$$

where Y is the outcome of interest for individual i ; SES is the principal factor from our standardised measure of social origin and, hence, β_1 reports the change in outcome propensity associated with having a one standard deviation higher social origin; $IDACI$ is a vector of binary variables reporting the young person’s IDACI quintile group, such that β'_2 reports a vector of changes in outcome propensity associated with membership of these different quintile groups (leaving the lowest deprivation group as an omitted category for comparison); \mathbf{X} is a varying vector of other covariates that adjust for potential confounding factors, and ε is an idiosyncratic error term with robust standard errors adjusted for study design as applicable. All analyses are weighted to ensure that estimates are nationally representative and account for non-response and attrition.

We ran variants of these models which varied the vector of additional covariates, as follows:

- M0 is a baseline model including only the social origin and social context variables (i.e., no additional covariates) to estimate the unadjusted inequalities in access to these tracks in each cohort.
- M1 adds covariates to adjust for cohort members’ other demographic characteristics, including ethnicity and gender; these principally seek to account for compositional differences between the cohorts as identified above.
- M2 adds covariates to adjust for young people’s prior education attainment at age 16, given the extremely important role of academic attainment in shaping selection into the academic track.

- Finally, M3 adds covariates to adjust for the subjects that cohort members studied between age 14 and 16 proxied by having studied for the full set of EBacc subjects, accounting for previous evidence that doing so may support progression into the academic track.

The results from M3 therefore provide a better basis for comparing the socioeconomic inequalities in access to A levels and facilitating subjects across cohorts, albeit that we acknowledge that there are likely to be residual confounding factors between them.

Results

We report estimated difference in entry to the academic track and enrolling in at least two facilitating subjects by SES quintile groups from M0 (providing ‘raw’ differences) and M3 (to provide fully ‘conditioned’ estimates) comparing across each of the three cohorts. For ease of interpretation and comparison, coefficients from the underlying probit models are converted to ‘average marginal effects’ (Arel-Bundock, 2025) to allow for interpretation as differences in predicted probability.

Table 3 reports average marginal effects in taking the academic track associated with social context and social origin with and without our full set of covariates (i.e., M0 and M3), *Table 4* reports the same inequalities in the probability of cohort members pursuing at least two facilitating subjects compared to the population and *Table 5* reports the same for inequalities in cohort members pursuing at least two facilitating subjects compared to other cohort members in the academic track. Results from the full set of models across each cohort can be referred to in *Appendix Tables 1-9*.

[Tables 3, 4, and 5 here]

Estimates from both our raw and conditioned models suggest that socio-economic inequalities in taking at least 3 A levels were similar across the NS and MCS cohorts, although larger for those in the COSMO cohort. An exception might be the relatively linear decrease in differences between Q1 and Q2 social origin students over time, but differences were consistently small. The larger differences in the COSMO cohort are potentially linked to the 2021 examination cancellations due to the COVID-19 pandemic: research has already established that this exacerbated existing SES inequalities (Anders et al., 2023) and evidence suggests that teacher-assessed GCSE grades during this time disproportionately benefitted students from higher SES groups (Wyness et al., 2022).

Inequalities are more pronounced for social origin than social context and are more consistently statistically significant. This could be due to the nature of the social context measure as an area-level, rather than individual-level, measure leading to more noise in the predictions. There is a relatively linear negative effect of social origin and social context after accounting for a set of other predictors including prior academic attainment. Put another way, being from a less advantaged social origin and/or social context both negatively predicted entering the academic track, consistent with previous literature. As hypothesised, this is the case across all three cohorts. Although the raw coefficients do suggest a decrease in the

predictive power of social origin over time, the final models including all relevant covariates do not, suggesting that there was little change over time in terms of inequalities.

Turning to inequalities in studying two facilitating subjects, cohort members from less advantaged social origin backgrounds were less likely than the highest social origin group to study two facilitating subjects, with some evidence of a reduction over time in our raw models. Consistent with inequalities in studying 3 A levels, we see larger socioeconomic gradients in the COSMO cohort, potentially due to inflated GCSE grades disproportionately benefitting higher SES students. However, when we add our full set of covariates – including prior attainment measured by best 8 GCSEs and studying the academically facilitating EBacc subjects – to our models, we see that the socioeconomic gradient is reduced in all three of our cohorts, and particularly so in NS. Consequently, in our conditioned models (*Tables 4 and 5*), there is little evidence of a reduction in inequality between the NS and MCS cohorts in terms of studying facilitating subjects over time when comparing similar individuals.

There was no suggestion of a strong relationship between social context and studying facilitating subjects. In fact, when comparing facilitating subject takers among the academic track cohort members to all other academic track cohort members, pupils from lower social contexts, especially Q3 and Q5, were the most likely to study facilitating subjects.

Discussion and Conclusions

In this paper, we have examined changes over time in social inequalities in young people's probabilities of entering the 'academic track' at age 16 in England by harmonising data from three English cohorts. We interpret the results as providing little evidence of change in the social inequalities of this education pathway among English young people.

Across all three studies, as expected, low social origin young people were less likely than their higher social origin peers to select the academic track (participation in the 'academic track' of studying for three A levels) and less likely to study two 'facilitating subjects' for A levels. Generally, this was a linear trend across quintile groups: the gap increased as differences in social origin widened when modelling the decision to take three A levels. For this outcome, there was little difference in the direction or strength of this relationship over time. While the COSMO results suggest an increase in social inequalities, this could be driven by grade inflation in GCSE grades which disproportionately benefitted students from higher SES backgrounds. Focusing on the intensive margin of young people studying at least two facilitating subjects, again both raw and conditioned results are consistent with little change over time.

The relationship between social context and decisions made at age 16 was comparatively weaker and more inconsistent than the relationship with social origin. This is not surprising: whereas the social origin variable is a composite of three parent-level factors which are specific to each young person, the social context variable is a neighbourhood level factor (representing ~1,500 households) which are not necessarily representative of the experiences of each young person. In some cases, young people from Q3 social origin were more likely to study facilitating subjects than their Q1 peers. There are substantial geographical disparities across England in the extent that being low SES is associated with participating in facilitating qualifications and subjects. In particular, many areas in London have a low score for social origin but their young people typically outperform the rest of the country. This could

be due to easier access and proximity to suitable and high-performing schools. We plan to explore this issue and its implications for the interpretations of our findings further.

One potential reason for these findings could be differences in the quality and availability of career guidance and the need for lower SES young people to be more informed about the existence of a 'hidden curriculum' regarding A level subject selection. Career guidance in English schools may need to be personalised to the identity and background of young people, especially for families who do not have a history of sending members to universities and 'elite' degrees. At age 16, decision-making skills are still developing (Keating et al., 2023); therefore, young people should be supported as much as possible when making decisions with potentially lifelong consequences.

We acknowledge that this study faced a number of limitations, in particular stemming from the challenges of harmonising data between the three datasets, which included the following. First, the different GCSE grading systems experienced by the three cohorts which could have introduced error to our measurements in a way that differs across cohorts. Second, even with the inclusion of survey design and non-response weights, we are concerned about the potential for compositional differences between the samples. Existing research suggests that Next Steps cohort members were more likely to progress to higher education than the population they represent (Anders, 2012b). In addition, the COSMO dataset completed their GCSE examinations during the COVID-19 pandemic and research suggests that in precarious labour markets, young people are more likely to increase their levels of education (Petrongolo & San Segundo, 2002).

Future research with these cohort studies will consider the potentially important effect of the raising the participation age from 16 to 18. The NS cohort members experienced a participation age of 16-years-old while the MCS and COSMO members experienced participation ages of 18-years-old. This policy change was intended to improve young people's career prospects by requiring higher levels of education and training (thus increasing their levels of human capital) before entering the labour market. In particular, the intention was that this policy change would disproportionately increase the education levels of low SES young people, who were more likely to enter the labour market at age 16 (Crawford et al., 2011). It is not clear, however, whether there is evidence that these social inequalities have been mitigated by the change in the participation age, but we plan to return to this question in future work.

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Figures

Figure 1. Decision chart of education decisions to be made in England at age 16 and resulting pathways.

Tables

Table 1: Background characteristics of cohort members by whether they were on the ‘academic track’ of enrolling in at least 3 A levels.

	Not academic track			Academic track		
	<i>Next Steps</i> (63%; n = 3320)	<i>Millennium Cohort</i> <i>Study</i> (56%; n = 1684)	<i>COSMO</i> (44%; n = 1834)	<i>Next Steps</i> (37%; n = 1948)	<i>Millennium Cohort</i> <i>Study</i> (44%; n = 1624)	<i>COSMO</i> (56%; n = 2001)
<i>Social Origin</i>						
Q1 (High SES)	11% (370)	18% (357)	13% (323)	42% (737)	40% (678)	29% (843)
Q2	20% (630)	22% (405)	5.1% (76)	22% (406)	28% (453)	5.7% (96)
Q3	22% (708)	23% (410)	19% (406)	20% (385)	17% (270)	22% (446)
Q4	23% (735)	19% (298)	24% (475)	11% (240)	9.4% (151)	23% (371)
Q5 (Low SES)	24% (877)	17% (214)	38% (554)	5.4% (180)	5.8% (72)	20% (245)
<i>Social Context</i>						
Q1 (Low Deprivation)	24% (725)	18% (301)	7.5% (220)	41% (721)	36% (527)	14% (447)
Q2	23% (691)	24% (375)	9.8% (266)	30% (535)	25% (394)	17% (448)
Q3	24% (768)	20% (351)	16% (316)	17% (348)	18% (299)	16% (351)
Q4	16% (620)	18% (336)	25% (422)	8.7% (216)	13% (234)	24% (375)
Q5 (High Deprivation)	12% (516)	20% (321)	42% (610)	3.3% (128)	9.2% (170)	29% (380)
<i>Ethnicity</i>						
Asian	6.3% (607)	7.1% (214)	17% (186)	6.7% (331)	9.1% (233)	32% (326)
Black	1.0% (74)	4.0% (65)	9.7% (111)	1.0% (52)	3.5% (63)	10% (134)
Mixed/Other	1.7% (100)	4.6% (83)	4.9% (113)	2.3% (82)	6.0% (101)	6.0% (141)
White	91% (2539)	84% (1322)	69% (1424)	90% (1483)	81% (1227)	52% (1400)
<i>Female</i>	49% (1610)	48% (828)	51% (869)	54% (1049)	56% (914)	59% (1156)
<i>Best 8</i>	32 (13)	34 (12)	38 (15)	52 (7)	51 (8)	56 (11)
<i>EBacc</i>						
Eligible	23% (799)	33% (591)	35% (570)	67% (1,228)	70% (1,158)	63% (1,202)

Notes: Calculation of percentages, means and standard deviations are weighted using study-provided design, non-response and attrition weights

Table 2: Background characteristics of cohort members by whether they took 2 facilitating A levels

Characteristic	Did not take 2 facilitating A levels			Did not take 2 facilitating A levels (but on ‘academic track’)			Did take 2 facilitating A levels		
	<i>Next Steps</i> (81%; n = 4293)	<i>Millennium Cohort Study</i> (78%; n = 2459)	<i>COSMO</i> (71%; n = 2816)	<i>Next Steps</i> (48%; n = 973)	<i>Millennium Cohort Study</i> (50%; n = 775)	<i>COSMO</i> (47%; n = 982)	<i>Next Steps</i> (19%; n = 975)	<i>Millennium Cohort Study</i> (22%; n = 849)	<i>COSMO</i> (29%; n = 1019)
<i>Social Origin</i>									
Q1 (High SES)	16% (649)	24% (674)	17% (649)	32% (279)	38% (317)	24% (326)	51% (458)	41% (361)	35% (517)
Q2	21% (856)	24% (622)	5.5% (128)	25% (226)	28% (217)	6.0% (52)	19% (180)	28% (236)	5.4% (44)
Q3	22% (918)	22% (540)	20% (651)	23% (210)	18% (130)	22% (245)	17% (175)	16% (140)	22% (201)
Q4	21% (885)	16% (367)	25% (677)	14% (150)	9.1% (69)	25% (202)	8.1% (90)	9.8% (82)	21% (169)
Q5 (Low SES)	20% (985)	14% (256)	33% (711)	6.0% (108)	6.9% (42)	24% (157)	4.8% (72)	4.6% (30)	17% (88)
<i>Social Context</i>									
Q1 (Low Deprivation)	27% (1,053)	24% (579)	9.8% (423)	38% (328)	38% (278)	14% (203)	43% (393)	33% (249)	15% (244)
Q2	25% (952)	24% (564)	12% (465)	30% (261)	25% (189)	15% (199)	29% (274)	25% (205)	19% (249)
Q3	23% (952)	19% (475)	16% (501)	19% (184)	15% (124)	17% (185)	16% (164)	20% (175)	15% (166)
Q4	15% (740)	17% (447)	24% (609)	9% (120)	14% (111)	23% (187)	8.5% (96)	12% (123)	25% (188)
Q5 (High Deprivation)	11% (596)	16% (394)	38% (818)	4% (80)	7.8% (73)	31% (208)	2.9% (48)	11% (97)	27% (172)
<i>Ethnicity</i>									

Asian	6.1% (769)	7.3% (305)	19% (295)	5.4% (162)	8.0% (91)	22% (109)	7.9% (169)	10% (142)	41% (217)
Black	1.1% (106)	4.0% (96)	11% (186)	1.4% (32)	3.8% (31)	13% (75)	1% (20)	3.1% (32)	7.5% (59)
Mixed/Other	1.7% (142)	4.3% (115)	5.4% (180)	1.6% (42)	3.8% (32)	6.1% (67)	2.5% (40)	8.2% (69)	6.0% (74)
White	91% (3,276)	84% (1,943)	65% (2,155)	92% (737)	84% (621)	59% (731)	89% (746)	78% (606)	46% (669)
<i>Female</i>	51% (2,174)	52% (1,301)	55% (1,472)	58% (564)	60% (473)	62% (603)	50% (485)	51% (441)	55% (553)
<i>Best 8 EBacc</i>	35 (14)	38 (13)	43 (15)	49 (7)	49 (9)	51 (10)	55 (6)	54 (7)	61 (10)
Eligible	31% (1,327)	42% (1,098)	42% (1,075)	57% (528)	65% (507)	54% (505)	75% (700)	76% (651)	71% (697)

Notes: Calculation of percentages, means and standard deviations are weighted using study-provided design, non-response and attrition weights.

Table 3. Average marginal effects of main study predictors estimated from probit model of entering the academic track (studying at least 3 A levels).

	<i>Next Steps</i> (<i>n</i> = 5268)		<i>MCS</i> (<i>n</i> = 3308)		<i>COSMO</i> (<i>n</i> = 3835)	
	Raw	Condi- tioned	Raw	Condi- tioned	Raw	Condi- tioned
<i>Social Origin</i> (Ref: <i>SES High/Q1</i>)						
SES Q2	-0.283*** (-12.06)	-0.042** (-2.98)	-0.119*** (-4.76)	-0.023 (-1.24)	-0.130** (-2.58)	-0.004 (-0.10)
SES Q3	-0.320*** (-13.56)	-0.051** (-3.19)	-0.227*** (-7.85)	-0.040 (-1.90)	-0.202*** (-7.93)	-0.102*** (-4.47)
SES Q4	-0.421*** (-17.09)	-0.055** (-3.23)	-0.290*** (-9.58)	-0.054* (-2.16)	-0.289*** (-10.63)	-0.138*** (-5.47)
SES Q5 (Low SES)	-0.501*** (-19.83)	-0.077*** (-3.68)	-0.354*** (-10.67)	-0.043 (-1.27)	-0.399*** (-13.60)	-0.130*** (-4.24)
<i>Social Context</i> (Ref: <i>Least Deprived</i>)						
IDACI Q2	-0.030 (-1.51)	0.002 (0.12)	-0.135*** (-5.18)	-0.055** (-2.60)	-0.012 (-0.39)	0.001 (0.02)
IDACI Q3	-0.098*** (-4.72)	-0.030* (-2.09)	-0.147*** (-4.78)	-0.062** (-2.79)	-0.044 (-1.36)	-0.030 (-1.09)
IDACI Q4	-0.114*** (-4.60)	-0.022 (-1.09)	-0.146*** (-4.47)	-0.038 (-1.44)	-0.089** (-2.81)	-0.033 (-1.17)
IDACI Q5 (Most De- prived)	-0.170*** (-6.34)	-0.013 (-0.62)	-0.221*** (-6.27)	-0.078** (-2.79)	-0.103** (-3.20)	-0.046 (-1.63)

Notes. Regression models weighted using study-provided design, non-response and attrition weights, with inference adjusted to account for study stratification and clustering. Model counts (N) are reported unweighted. * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$, *** = $p < .001$. Other covariates are included (Ethnicity, Female, Age 16 average attainment and facilitating curriculum). See *Appendix Tables 1-3*. MCS = Millennium Cohort Study; COSMO = COVID Social Mobility and Opportunities study.

Table 4. Average marginal effects estimated from probit model of taking at least 2 facilitating A levels.

	<i>Next Steps</i> (<i>n</i> = 5272)		<i>MCS</i> (<i>n</i> = 3308)		<i>COSMO</i> (<i>n</i> = 3835)	
	Raw	Condi- tioned	Raw	Condi- tioned	Raw	Condi- tioned
<i>Social Origin</i> (Ref: <i>SES High/Q1</i>)						
SES Q2	-0.245*** (-10.39)	-0.046** (-3.38)	-0.072** (-3.26)	-0.002 (-0.13)	-0.101* (-1.98)	0.027 (0.62)
SES Q3	-0.260*** (-11.32)	-0.046** (-3.37)	-0.143*** (-6.46)	-0.018 (-0.91)	-0.218*** (-8.47)	-0.109*** (-4.72)
SES Q4	-0.320*** (-13.58)	-0.052** (-3.41)	-0.166*** (-6.45)	-0.012 (-0.45)	-0.282*** (-10.55)	-0.134*** (-5.24)
SES Q5 (Low SES)	-0.340*** (-13.69)	-0.042* (-2.03)	-0.229*** (-8.44)	-0.051 (-1.55)	-0.406*** (-15.16)	-0.167*** (-5.10)
<i>Social Context</i> (Ref: <i>Least De- prived</i>)						
IDACI Q2	-0.026 (-1.66)	-0.005 (-0.48)	-0.042* (-2.18)	0.003 (0.20)	-0.006 (-0.20)	0.004 (0.17)
IDACI Q3	-0.057 ** (-3.05)	-0.011 (-0.87)	-0.008 (-0.32)	0.043* (2.14)	-0.039 (-1.28)	-0.031 (-1.17)
IDACI Q4	-0.059** (-2.88)	-0.008 (-0.48)	-0.049 (-1.91)	0.014 (0.67)	-0.085** (-2.84)	-0.042 (-1.50)
IDACI Q5 (Most De- prived)	-0.101*** (-4.62)	0.004 (0.14)	-0.050 (-1.67)	0.034 (1.16)	-0.115*** (-3.83)	-0.068* (-2.49)

Notes. Regression models weighted using study-provided design, non-response and attrition weights, with inference adjusted to account for study stratification and clustering. Model counts (N) are reported unweighted. * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$, *** = $p < .001$. Other covariates are included (Ethnicity, Female, Age 16 average attainment and facilitating curriculum). See *Appendix Tables 1-3*. MCS = Millennium Cohort Study; COSMO = COVID Social Mobility and Opportunities study.

Table 5. Average marginal effects estimated from probit model of taking at least 2 facilitating A levels (conditional on taking at least 3 A levels).

	<i>Next Steps (n = 1948)</i>		<i>MCS (n = 1624)</i>		<i>COSMO (n = 2001)</i>	
	Raw	Condi- tioned	Raw	Condi- tioned	Raw	Condi- tioned
<i>Social Origin</i> (Ref: SES High/Q1)						
SES Q2	-0.189*** (-5.37)	-0.086** (-2.68)	-0.024 (-0.72)	0.009 (0.29)	0.014 (0.35)	0.065 (1.24)
SES Q3	-0.185*** (-5.74)	-0.079** (-2.75)	-0.066 (-1.79)	-0.008 (-0.22)	-0.097*** (-3.40)	-0.079** (-3.03)
SES Q4	-0.249*** (-6.22)	-0.101** (-2.74)	-0.036 (-0.63)	0.035 (0.64)	-0.093** (-2.74)	-0.066* (-2.18)
SES Q5 (Low SES)	-0.167** (-2.80)	-0.043 (-0.85)	-0.159* (-2.05)	-0.082 (-1.20)	-0.237*** (-4.81)	-0.159*** (-4.29)
<i>Social Context</i> (Ref: Least Deprived)						
IDACI Q2	-0.032 (-1.04)	-0.015 (-0.58)	0.035 (1.00)	0.045 (1.45)	0.008 (0.28)	0.001 (0.02)
IDACI Q3	-0.028 (-0.70)	-0.002 (-0.07)	0.130** (3.35)	0.141*** (3.66)	-0.009 (-0.27)	-0.013 (-0.41)
IDACI Q4	-0.006 (-0.15)	0.002 (0.05)	0.034 (0.71)	0.057 (1.34)	-0.032 (-0.95)	-0.038 (-1.18)
IDACI Q5 (Most Deprived)	-0.039 (-0.63)	0.034 (0.51)	0.150** (2.72)	0.141* (2.48)	-0.070 (-1.88)	-0.070* (-2.16)

Notes. Regression models weighted using study-provided design, non-response and attrition weights, with inference adjusted to account for study stratification and clustering. Model counts (N) are reported unweighted. * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$, *** = $p < .001$. Other covariates are included (Ethnicity, Female, Age 16 average attainment and facilitating curriculum). See *Appendix Tables 1-3*. MCS = Millennium Cohort Study; COSMO = COVID Social Mobility and Opportunities study.

Appendix Tables

Appendix Table 1: Average marginal effects estimated from probit model of taking at least A levels in the Next Steps dataset.

	M0	M1	M2	M3
<i>Social Origin</i>				
<i>(Ref: SES High/Q1)</i>				
SES Q2	-0.283*** (-12.06)	-0.282*** (-12.16)	-0.043** (-3.04)	-0.042** (-2.98)
SES Q3	-0.320*** (-13.56)	-0.318*** (-13.72)	-0.053*** (-3.35)	-0.051** (-3.19)
SES Q4	-0.421*** (-17.09)	-0.422*** (-17.40)	-0.058*** (-3.42)	-0.055** (-3.23)
SES Q5 (Low SES)	-0.501*** (-19.83)	-0.516*** (-20.69)	-0.080*** (-3.87)	-0.077*** (-3.68)
<i>Social Context</i>				
<i>(Ref: Least Deprived)</i>				
IDACI Q2	-0.030 (-1.51)	-0.033 (-1.63)	0.002 (0.12)	0.002 (0.12)
IDACI Q3	-0.098*** (-4.72)	-0.109*** (-5.16)	-0.033* (-2.24)	-0.030* (-2.09)
IDACI Q4	-0.114*** (-4.60)	-0.139*** (-5.60)	-0.023 (-1.14)	-0.022 (-1.09)
IDACI Q5 (Most Deprived)	-0.170*** (-6.34)	-0.199*** (-7.39)	-0.016 (-0.74)	-0.013 (-0.62)
<i>Ethnicity (Ref: White)</i>				
Asian		0.158*** (6.54)	0.072*** (3.71)	0.070*** (3.64)
Black		0.100 (1.67)	0.035 (0.91)	0.035 (0.88)
Mixed/Other		0.053 (1.31)	-0.034 (-1.13)	-0.037 (-1.25)
<i>Gender (Ref: Male)</i>				
Female		0.049** (3.11)	-0.018 (-1.38)	-0.017 (-1.28)
<i>Age 16 average attainment</i>				
			0.023*** (59.76)	0.023*** (51.43)
<i>Age 16 facilitating curriculum</i>				
<i>(Ref: Non-facilitating)</i>				
Facilitating				0.033** (2.72)
N	5268	5268	5268	5268
Residual degrees of freedom	604	604	604	604

Notes: Regression models are weighted using study-provided design, non-response and attrition weights, with inferences adjusted to account for study stratification and clustering; model counts (N) are reported unweighted. * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$, *** = $p < .001$.

Appendix Table 2: Average marginal effects estimated from probit model of taking at least A levels in the Millennium Cohort Study dataset.

	M0	M1	M2	M3
<i>Social Origin</i>				
<i>(Ref: SES High/Q1)</i>				
SES Q2	-0.119*** (-4.76)	-0.112*** (-4.53)	-0.026 (-1.36)	-0.023 (-1.24)
SES Q3	-0.227*** (-7.85)	-0.232*** (-8.14)	-0.040 (-1.89)	-0.040 (-1.90)
SES Q4	-0.290*** (-9.58)	-0.304*** (-10.18)	-0.054* (-2.15)	-0.054* (-2.16)
SES Q5 (Low SES)	-0.354*** (-10.67)	-0.370*** (-11.26)	-0.043 (-1.31)	-0.043 (-1.27)
<i>Social Context</i>				
<i>(Ref: Least Deprived)</i>				
IDACI Q2	-0.135*** (-5.18)	-0.137*** (-5.22)	-0.055* (-2.58)	-0.055** (-2.60)
IDACI Q3	-0.147*** (-4.78)	-0.160*** (-5.40)	-0.063** (-2.86)	-0.062** (-2.79)
IDACI Q4	-0.146*** (-4.47)	-0.176*** (-5.49)	-0.041 (-1.58)	-0.038 (-1.44)
IDACI Q5 (Most Deprived)	-0.199*** (-5.48)	-0.229*** (-6.44)	-0.080** (-2.87)	-0.078** (-2.79)
<i>Ethnicity (Ref: White)</i>				
Asian		0.179*** (5.31)	0.103*** (3.65)	0.100** (3.50)
Black		0.102 (1.78)	0.052 (1.13)	0.047 (0.97)
Mixed/Other		0.150** (3.04)	0.068* (1.99)	0.067* (1.97)
<i>Gender (Ref: Male)</i>				
Female		0.074*** (4.41)	0.007 (0.47)	0.005 (0.31)
<i>Age 16 average attainment</i>				
			0.024*** (56.01)	0.023*** (43.90)
<i>Age 16 facilitating curriculum</i>				
<i>(Ref: Non-facilitating)</i>				
Facilitating				0.042* (2.49)
N	3308	3308	3308	3308
Residual degrees of freedom	212	212	212	212

Notes: Regression models are weighted using study-provided design, non-response and attrition weights, with inferences adjusted to account for study stratification and clustering; model counts (N) are reported unweighted. * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$, *** = $p < .001$.

Appendix Table 3: Average marginal effects estimated from probit model of taking at least A levels in the COSMO dataset.

	M0	M1	M2	M3
<i>Social Origin</i>				
<i>(Ref: SES High/Q1)</i>				
SES Q2	-0.130** (-2.58)	-0.132** (-2.86)	-0.005 (-0.11)	-0.004 (-0.10)
SES Q3	-0.202*** (-7.93)	-0.193*** (-8.45)	-0.102*** (-4.49)	-0.102*** (-4.47)
SES Q4	-0.289*** (-10.63)	-0.272*** (-11.28)	-0.139*** (-5.51)	-0.138*** (-5.47)
SES Q5 (Low SES)	-0.399*** (-13.60)	-0.378*** (-13.53)	-0.132*** (-4.29)	-0.130*** (-4.24)
<i>Social Context</i>				
<i>(Ref: Least Deprived)</i>				
IDACI Q2	-0.012 (-0.39)	-0.013 (-0.44)	0.001 (0.04)	0.001 (0.02)
IDACI Q3	-0.044 (-1.36)	-0.049 (-1.57)	-0.030 (-1.08)	-0.030 (-1.09)
IDACI Q4	-0.089** (-2.81)	-0.101*** (-3.31)	-0.035 (-1.22)	-0.033 (-1.17)
IDACI Q5 (Most Deprived)	-0.103** (-3.20)	-0.119*** (-3.81)	-0.047 (-1.65)	-0.046 (-1.63)
<i>Ethnicity (Ref: White)</i>				
Asian		0.155*** (5)	0.04 (1.75)	0.043 (1.67)
Black		0.083* (2.22)	0.057 (1.65)	0.054 (1.56)
Mixed/Other		0.021 (0.58)	0.006 (0.15)	0.005 (0.13)
<i>Gender (Ref: Male)</i>				
Female		0.117*** (6.12)	0.020 (1.13)	0.020 (1.09)
<i>Age 16 average attainment</i>				
			0.014*** (19.1)	0.014*** (18.23)
<i>Age 16 facilitating curriculum</i>				
<i>(Ref: Non-facilitating)</i>				
Facilitating				0.021 (1.25)
N	3835	3835	3835	3835
Residual degrees of freedom	2200	2200	2200	2200

Notes: Regression models are weighted using study-provided design, non-response and attrition weights, with inferences adjusted to account for study stratification and clustering; model counts (N) are reported unweighted. * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$, *** = $p < .001$.

Appendix Table 4: Average marginal effects estimated from probit model of taking at least 2 facilitating A levels in the Next Steps dataset.

	M0	M1	M2	M3
<i>Social Origin</i>				
<i>(Ref: SES High/Q1)</i>				
SES Q2	-0.245*** (-10.39)	-0.251*** (-10.32)	-0.048*** (-3.50)	-0.046** (-3.38)
SES Q3	-0.260*** (-11.32)	-0.267*** (-11.53)	-0.049*** (-3.60)	-0.046** (-3.37)
SES Q4	-0.320*** (-13.58)	-0.333*** (-13.87)	-0.056*** (-3.74)	-0.052** (-3.41)
SES Q5 (Low SES)	-0.340*** (-13.69)	-0.361*** (-14.36)	-0.046* (-2.21)	-0.042* (-2.03)
<i>Social Context</i>				
<i>(Ref: Least Deprived)</i>				
IDACI Q2	-0.026 (-1.66)	-0.029 (-1.72)	-0.006 (-0.50)	-0.005 (-0.48)
IDACI Q3	-0.057 ** (-3.05)	-0.066** (-3.30)	-0.013 (-1.01)	-0.011 (-0.87)
IDACI Q4	-0.059** (-2.88)	-0.083*** (-4.02)	-0.008 (-0.45)	-0.008 (-0.48)
IDACI Q5 (Most Deprived)	-0.101*** (-4.62)	-0.124*** (-5.23)	0.001 (0.03)	0.004 (0.14)
<i>Ethnicity (Ref: White)</i>				
Asian		0.146*** (5.84)	0.087** (3.47)	0.085** (3.50)
Black		0.021 (0.46)	-0.007 (-0.27)	-0.009 (-0.32)
Mixed/Other		0.071 (1.87)	-0.007 (-0.38)	-0.007 (-0.37)
<i>Gender (Ref: Male)</i>				
Female		-0.002 (-0.13)	-0.054*** (-5.47)	-0.054*** (-5.33)
<i>Age 16 average attainment</i>				
			0.019*** (37.64)	0.018*** (33.83)
<i>Age 16 facilitating curriculum</i>				
<i>(Ref: Non-facilitating)</i>				
Facilitating				0.036** (3.16)
N	5268	5268	5268	5268
Residual degrees of freedom	604	604	604	604

Notes: Regression models are weighted using study-provided design, non-response and attrition weights, with inferences adjusted to account for study stratification and clustering; model counts (N) are reported unweighted. * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$, *** = $p < .001$.

Appendix Table 5: Average marginal effects estimated from probit model of taking at least 2 facilitating A levels in the Millennium Cohort Study dataset.

	M0	M1	M2	M3
<i>Social Origin</i>				
<i>(Ref: SES High/Q1)</i>				
SES Q2	-0.072** (-3.26)	-0.068** (-3.02)	-0.004 (-0.25)	-0.002 (-0.13)
SES Q3	-0.143*** (-6.46)	-0.150*** (-6.72)	-0.019 (-0.96)	-0.018 (-0.91)
SES Q4	-0.166*** (-6.45)	-0.179*** (-6.76)	-0.012 (-0.46)	-0.012 (-0.45)
SES Q5 (Low SES)	-0.229*** (-8.44)	-0.244*** (-9.59)	-0.054 (-1.71)	-0.051 (-1.55)
<i>Social Context</i>				
<i>(Ref: Least Deprived)</i>				
IDACI Q2	-0.042* (-2.18)	-0.047* (-2.36)	0.004 (0.23)	0.003 (0.20)
IDACI Q3	-0.008 (-0.32)	-0.022 (-0.89)	0.042* (2.10)	0.043* (2.14)
IDACI Q4	-0.049 (-1.91)	-0.073** (-2.82)	0.012 (0.57)	0.014 (0.67)
IDACI Q5 (Most Deprived)	-0.034 (-1.11)	-0.058 (-1.87)	0.033 (1.17)	0.034 (1.16)
<i>Ethnicity (Ref: White)</i>				
Asian		0.146*** (4.51)	0.093** (3.34)	0.089** (3.17)
Black		0.036 (0.93)	0.018 (0.54)	0.014 (0.42)
Mixed/Other		0.188*** (3.92)	0.118** (3.32)	0.118** (3.27)
<i>Gender (Ref: Male)</i>				
Female		-0.002 (-0.11)	-0.045** (-3.38)	-0.048*** (-3.65)
<i>Age 16 average attainment</i>				
			0.019*** (35.76)	0.018*** (31.81)
<i>Age 16 facilitating curriculum</i>				
<i>(Ref: Non-facilitating)</i>				
Facilitating				0.043** (2.87)
N	3308	3308	3308	3308
Residual degrees of freedom	212	212	212	212

Notes: Regression models are weighted using study-provided design, non-response and attrition weights, with inferences adjusted to account for study stratification and clustering; model counts (N) are reported unweighted. * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$, *** = $p < .001$.

Appendix Table 6: Average marginal effects estimated from probit model of taking at least 2 facilitating A levels in the COSMO dataset.

	M0	M1	M2	M3
<i>Social Origin</i>				
<i>(Ref: SES High/Q1)</i>				
SES Q2	-0.101*	-0.095*	0.026	0.027
	(-1.98)	(-2.12)	(0.61)	(0.62)
SES Q3	-0.218***	-0.195***	-0.109***	-0.109***
	(-8.47)	(-8.78)	(-4.75)	(-4.72)
SES Q4	-0.282***	-0.259***	-0.135***	-0.134***
	(-10.55)	(-11.04)	(-5.28)	(-5.24)
SES Q5 (Low SES)	-0.406***	-0.404***	-0.169***	-0.167***
	(-15.16)	(-14.34)	(-5.18)	(-5.10)
<i>Social Context</i>				
<i>(Ref: Least Deprived)</i>				
IDACI Q2	-0.006	-0.007	0.005	0.004
	(-0.20)	(-0.25)	(0.2)	(0.17)
IDACI Q3	-0.039	-0.046	-0.030	-0.031
	(-1.28)	(-1.57)	(-1.14)	(-1.17)
IDACI Q4	-0.085**	-0.101***	-0.046	-0.042
	(-2.84)	(-3.47)	(-1.62)	(-1.50)
IDACI Q5 (Most Deprived)	-0.115***	-0.135***	-0.069*	-0.068*
	(-3.83)	(-4.57)	(-2.54)	(-2.49)
<i>Ethnicity (Ref: White)</i>				
Asian		0.187***	0.082***	0.078**
		(6.86)	(3.42)	(3.25)
Black		0.087*	0.060	0.054
		(2.34)	(1.68)	(1.52)
Mixed/Other		0.031	0.020	0.018
		(0.9)	(0.49)	(0.46)
<i>Gender (Ref: Male)</i>				
Female		0.058**	-0.033	-0.034
		(3.05)	(-1.74)	(-1.80)
<i>Age 16 average attainment</i>				
			0.014***	0.013***
			(16.75)	(15.68)
<i>Age 16 facilitating curriculum</i>				
<i>(Ref: Non-facilitating)</i>				
Facilitating				0.040*
				(2.47)
N	3835	3835	3835	3835
Residual degrees of freedom	2200	2200	2200	2200

Notes: Regression models are weighted using study-provided design, non-response and attrition weights, with inferences adjusted to account for study stratification and clustering; model counts (N) are reported unweighted. * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$, *** = $p < .001$.

Appendix Table 7: Average marginal effects estimated from probit model of taking at least 2 facilitating A levels (conditional on taking at least 3 A levels) in the Next Steps dataset.

	M0	M1	M2	M3
<i>Social Origin</i>				
<i>(Ref: SES High/Q1)</i>				
SES Q2	-0.189*** (-5.37)	-0.180*** (-5.14)	-0.089** (-2.80)	-0.086** (-2.68)
SES Q3	-0.185*** (-5.74)	-0.183*** (-5.79)	-0.083** (-2.89)	-0.079** (-2.75)
SES Q4	-0.249*** (-6.22)	-0.251*** (-6.30)	-0.108** (-2.98)	-0.101** (-2.74)
SES Q5 (Low SES)	-0.167** (-2.80)	-0.202*** (-3.50)	-0.048 (-0.94)	-0.043 (-0.85)
<i>Social Context</i>				
<i>(Ref: Least Deprived)</i>				
IDACI Q2	-0.032 (-1.04)	-0.029 (-0.97)	-0.017 (-0.65)	-0.015 (-0.58)
IDACI Q3	-0.028 (-0.70)	-0.029 (-0.73)	-0.005 (-0.15)	-0.002 (-0.07)
IDACI Q4	-0.006 (-0.15)	-0.039 (-0.92)	0.005 (0.13)	0.002 (0.05)
IDACI Q5 (Most Deprived)	-0.039 (-0.63)	-0.062 (-0.92)	0.032 (0.48)	0.034 (0.51)
<i>Ethnicity (Ref: White)</i>				
Asian		0.159*** (3.97)	0.170** (3.57)	0.170*** (3.60)
Black		-0.029 (-0.33)	-0.037 (-0.53)	-0.037 (-0.53)
Mixed/Other		0.147* (2.21)	0.044 (0.81)	0.050 (0.91)
<i>Gender (Ref: Male)</i>				
Female		-0.072** (-2.94)	-0.122*** (-6.01)	-0.122*** (-5.97)
<i>Age 16 average attainment</i>				
			0.029**** (18.21)	0.028*** (16.17)
<i>Age 16 facilitating curriculum</i>				
<i>(Ref: Non-facilitating)</i>				
Facilitating				0.058* (2.12)
N	1948	1948	1948	1948
Residual degrees of freedom	483	483	483	483

Notes: Regression models are weighted using study-provided design, non-response and attrition weights, with inferences adjusted to account for study stratification and clustering; model counts (N) are reported unweighted. * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$, *** = $p < .001$.

Appendix Table 8: Average marginal effects estimated from probit model of taking at least 2 facilitating A levels (conditional on taking at least 3 A levels) in the Millennium Cohort Study dataset.

	M0	M1	M2	M3
<i>Social Origin</i>				
<i>(Ref: SES High/Q1)</i>				
SES Q2	-0.024 (-0.72)	-0.024 (-0.72)	0.006 (0.20)	0.009 (0.29)
SES Q3	-0.066 (-1.79)	-0.064 (-1.74)	-0.009 (-0.24)	-0.008 (-0.22)
SES Q4	-0.036 (-0.63)	-0.039 (-0.66)	0.035 (0.64)	0.035 (0.64)
SES Q5 (Low SES)	-0.159* (-2.05)	-0.165* (-2.46)	-0.090 (-1.34)	-0.082 (-1.20)
<i>Social Context</i>				
<i>(Ref: Least Deprived)</i>				
IDACI Q2	0.035 (1.00)	0.028 (0.82)	0.047 (1.52)	0.045 (1.45)
IDACI Q3	0.130** (3.35)	0.120** (2.97)	0.142*** (3.66)	0.141*** (3.66)
IDACI Q4	0.034 (0.71)	0.016 (0.33)	0.054 (1.28)	0.057 (1.34)
IDACI Q5 (Most Deprived)	0.150** (2.72)	0.135* (2.43)	0.143* (2.52)	0.141* (2.48)
<i>Ethnicity (Ref: White)</i>				
Asian		0.075 (1.41)	0.091 (1.89)	0.087 (1.77)
Black		-0.048 (-0.84)	-0.020 (-0.34)	-0.021 (-0.37)
Mixed/Other		0.191** (3.01)	0.174** (2.98)	0.176** (2.96)
<i>Gender (Ref: Male)</i>				
Female		-0.091** (-3.41)	-0.096*** (-3.61)	-0.099*** (-3.76)
<i>Age 16 average attainment</i>				
			0.019*** (13.41)	0.018*** (12.16)
<i>Age 16 facilitating curriculum</i>				
<i>(Ref: Non-facilitating)</i>				
Facilitating				0.049 (1.63)
N	1624	1624	1624	1624
Residual degrees of freedom	212	212	212	212

Notes: Regression models are weighted using study-provided design, non-response and attrition weights, with inferences adjusted to account for study stratification and clustering; model counts (N) are reported unweighted. * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$, *** = $p < .001$.

Appendix Table 9: Average marginal effects estimated from probit model of taking at least 2 facilitating A levels (conditional on taking at least 3 A levels) in the COSMO dataset.

	M0	M1	M2	M3
<i>Social Origin</i>				
<i>(Ref: SES High/Q1)</i>				
SES Q2	0.014 (0.35)	0.013 (0.27)	0.066 (1.27)	0.065 (1.24)
SES Q3	-0.097*** (-3.40)	-0.094*** (-3.54)	-0.079** (-3.03)	-0.079** (-3.03)
SES Q4	-0.093** (-2.74)	-0.097** (-3.09)	-0.068* (-2.22)	-0.066* (-2.18)
SES Q5 (Low SES)	-0.237*** (-4.81)	-0.222*** (-6.12)	-0.159*** (-4.31)	-0.159*** (-4.29)
<i>Social Context</i>				
<i>(Ref: Least Deprived)</i>				
IDACI Q2	0.008 (0.28)	0.008 (0.27)	0.001 (0.03)	0.001 (0.02)
IDACI Q3	-0.009 (-0.27)	-0.015 (-0.44)	-0.015 (-0.44)	-0.013 (-0.41)
IDACI Q4	-0.032 (-0.95)	-0.044 (-1.34)	-0.045 (-1.40)	-0.038 (-1.18)
IDACI Q5 (Most Deprived)	-0.070 (-1.88)	-0.082* (-2.42)	-0.071* (-2.21)	-0.070* (-2.16)
<i>Ethnicity (Ref: White)</i>				
Asian		0.152*** (4.47)	0.111*** (3.51)	0.106*** (3.35)
Black		0.054 (1.38)	0.054 (1.41)	0.048 (1.28)
Mixed/Other		0.027 (0.68)	0.021 (0.5)	0.019 (0.47)
<i>Gender (Ref: Male)</i>				
Female		-0.073*** (-3.42)	-0.097*** (-4.36)	-0.097*** (-4.37)
<i>Age 16 average attainment</i>				
			0.008*** (6.87)	0.007*** (6.09)
<i>Age 16 facilitating curriculum</i>				
<i>(Ref: Non-facilitating)</i>				
Facilitating				0.048* (2.15)
N	2001	2001	2001	2001
Residual degrees of freedom	1254	1254	1254	1254

Notes: Regression models are weighted using study-provided design, non-response and attrition weights, with inferences adjusted to account for study stratification and clustering; model counts (N) are reported unweighted. * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$, *** = $p < .001$.